

2. Agroforestry in the EU Forest Strategy

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EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](https://www.transparencyregister.eu/etn/913270437706-82)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries (see euraf.net).

While EURAF welcomes mentions of agroforestry in the Forestry Strategy 2030, however we note that the two previous strategies have also stressed the importance of agroforestry without converting this to targets in their Action Plans. Trees outside Forests (ToF) are crucial to Europe's environment and adaptation/mitigation to climate change. However, Member States are very bad at monitoring and valuing them. Proposals are given to focus tree planting on current "tree deserts", which are also the areas of greatest environmental stress. Taking the priority areas, with 4-5 environmental stresses, EURAF estimates that an additional 3.13 million trees should be planted outside the forest b 2030.

1 The New EU Forest Strategy

EURAF was delighted to learn from the “European Green Deal” that there is to be another “New Forest Strategy” to replace the 2013 “New Forest Strategy”. Sadly, we conclude that these Strategies have done little to promote the uptake of agroforestry by Member States over the past 25 years.

Back in 1998, the first Forestry Strategy ([COM 1998/649](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/1998/649)) included four mentions of agroforestry:

- (p15) called for an emphasis on ‘The sustainable and multifunctional management of forests, analysis, methods and suitable indicators, the appropriate afforestation, management and exploitation techniques and methods, the genetic improvement of trees for better growth, resistance and quality, and the optimisation of **agroforestry systems**’.
- (p16) asked for research to concentrate on ‘multifunctional management of forests: support to forest policy issues; diversification (non-wood uses, **agrosilvopastoral systems**), multifunctional and sustainable management combining quality production with conservation and protection. Forest ecosystems biodiversity and protection of forest soils.
- (p20) recognised that ‘maintenance of traditional management of **silvopastoral systems** with high levels of biodiversity which may be lost if these areas are abandoned (e.g. in the Mediterranean regions)’
- and (p23) mentioned the importance of **agroforestry for carbon sequestration**.

Yet these aims were forgotten. The 2005 evaluation of the Strategy (European Commission, 2005) did not use the word agroforestry, let alone check progress. The 2006 “EU Forest Action Plan” (European Commission, 2006) again invited Member States to “promote agroforestry systems” in their rural development programmes. And again, there was no mention of agroforestry in any of the 145 pages of its 2012 evaluation (Paivi et al., 2012).

By the time the 2013 “New Forestry Strategy” appeared (European Commission, 2013), the pattern of promptly forgotten calls for actions was set - and, of course, followed. Agroforestry was introduced in the context of the national Rural Development Programmes, but, yet again, omitted from all targets in the Multi-Annual Implementation Plan (European Commission, 2015).

But hope springs eternal. The European Commission has recently recognized that it is not enough to include the word ‘agroforestry’ in a European Strategy and hope that Member States will take it up. The mid-term evaluation of the 2013 Forestry Strategy (European Commission, 2018) concluded that:

*The uptake of certain measures (e.g. **agroforestry**, Natura 2000) has so far not achieved the expected results. Additional exchange and promotion of good practices across and within Member States might help address potential limiting factors, often attributed to administrative burden or forest ownership structure. The proposal for the CAP 2021-2027, by providing more subsidiarity and flexibility, should bring new opportunities for Member States to design measures that better support local needs and priorities with simpler administrative procedures.*

Similarly, the mid-term evaluation of all CAP Forestry Programmes (Alliance Environnement, 2017) agreed that implementation of the agroforestry sub-measure (8.2) had been disappointing, but added:

This sub-measure appears to be an important potential tool for the implementation of new management practices. Agroforestry could provide new economic opportunities in marginal farming areas, deliver significant additional ecosystem services and biodiversity benefits, and lead to better adaptation of farming systems to climate change. Hence, in the evaluator's opinion, its importance may rise in the coming years, provided that a sufficient level of incentive is included in the premium and technical advice is readily available

2 Trees Outside the Forest

A comprehensive “Forestry Strategy” should include “Trees outside Forests (ToF)”. The concept of Trees outside Forests encompasses not only trees in agroforestry systems, but also urban trees. In the aggregate, across Europe, we are talking about billions of extra trees. The only reason ToF is out of scope in a Forestry Strategy is because of the silo thinking which has bedevilled forestry and agricultural departments in Brussels and in the Member States for what seems like forever. These silos lead to huge problems. For example, the [Biodiversity Strategy's](#) promise to plant 3 billion extra trees could become an environmental disaster if all of those trees are planted as monocultures. If, however, a significant fraction of the 3 billion trees are planted or regenerated on agricultural and urban lands, they would add a great range of ecosystem services. It is therefore imperative to extend the scope of the new strategy.

How could the Strategy break these silos in Member States, the Commission and in industry? A strong signal would be to include a discrete section in the new strategy about agroforestry. It should include explicit, numerical targets or percentages for some (or, perhaps, all) of the 3 billion new trees to be planted **outside of forest land**.

Country	Forest%	OWL%	OLTC%
Aust	96.2	3.8	0
Belgium	95	5	0
Bulgaria	97.5	0.6	1.9
Croatia	71.3	21.1	7.6
Czech Republic	96.5	0	3.5
Denmark	92.6	6.9	0.5
Estonia	90.9	9.1	0
Finland	96.6	3.4	1
France	94.9	3.3	1.8
Germany	89.1	0	10.9
Greece	61.9	38.1	0
Hungary	90.2	5.3	4.5
Ireland	94.1	5.9	0
Italy	83.7	16.3	0
Latvia	96	3.2	0.8
Lithuania	92.9	4.4	2.7
Luxemburg	98.4	1.6	0
Malta	100	0	0
Netherlands	100	0	0
Poland	100	0	0
Portugal	64.8	35.2	0
Romania	89.6	1.2	9.2
Slovakia	87.6	0	12.4
Slovenia	95.7	1.8	2.5
Spain	65.7	32.9	1.4
Sweden	89.4	7.8	2.8
Average	89.6	8.0	2.4

The EU definition of agroforestry is “a land use system in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land” (Reg 1305/2013), and the constitution of the European Agroforestry Federation clarifies that ... “Agroforestry practices include all forms of association of trees and crops (silvoarable systems) and/or animals (silvopastoral systems), on a parcel of agricultural land, whether in the interior of the parcel or on its edges (hedgess)”.

Table 1: National returns to the FAO Forest Resource Assessment showing “Forest”, “Other Wooded Land” and “Other Land With Tree Cover” (FAO, 2015). It shows only blocks of woodland greater than 0.5ha.

According to the estimates of [den Herder et al. \(2017\)](#), using the LUCAS database, the total area under agroforestry in the EU 27 is about 15.4 million ha which is equivalent to about 3.6% of the territorial area and 8.8% of the utilised agricultural area. The FAO 2015 Forest Resource Assessment for EU member states (Table 1), shows that at least 10% of the tree hectareage is not on “official” forest land, and this is likely to be a significant underestimate since groups of trees less than 0.5ha or tree strips less than 20 m wide are excluded from national FAO returns.

Even the English Government has recognised the need to look at trees outside the forest, and a consultation has just been completed on an “England Tree Strategy” (DEFRA, 2020), to replace a previous “forest” strategy. The importance of agroforestry is also recognised by the European Parliament. [29 amendments](#) adding “agroforestry” were received by July 2020 to Parliament’s Own Opinion Report titled “*European Forest Strategy the way*

forward". ([2019/2157 - INI](#)). Decisions on the final text will be made in a plenary session of Parliament in October 2020.

3 What targets are needed for agroforestry?

Four quantitative approaches have assessed the potential for agroforestry expansion in the European Union:

1. [Aertsens et al \(2013\)](#) (*a first assessment of EU carbon sequestration potential with AF*) The paper by Aertstems et al. ([2013](#)) was primarily focused on estimating carbon sequestration. They assumed that agroforestry was possible on half of EU arable land (90 Mha) and permanent pastures (50 Mha), and recommended including an additional 17.8 M kilometres of hedges into the EU.
2. [Reisner et al \(2007\)](#) (*an early estimate of priority areas for silvoarable AF*) focused on silvoarable agroforestry (SAF), taking data on soil, climate, topography, and land cover to identify agroforestry target regions where: (i) productive growth of trees (*Juglans spp.*, *Prunus avium*, *Populus spp.*, *Pinus pinea*, and *Quercus ilex*) in SAF systems could be expected and where (ii) SAF systems could potentially reduce the risk of soil erosion, nitrate leaching and increase landscape diversity.¹ They showed that silvoarable systems could grow productively on 56% of arable land in Europe (i.e. 90.79 Mha),² with a bigger figure if more tree species are included. EURAF suggested at the time that **90 Mha was a reasonable target figure for the maximum extent of silvoarable agroforestry (SAF) in the EU27.**
3. [Kay et al \(2019\)](#) (*an environmental pressure approach to finding AF areas for carbon mitigation*) estimated the priority areas for agroforestry, classified by biogeographical regions. They calculated detailed environmental pressures on 100 x 100m pixels across Europe. Areas with more than 4 (pastures) or 5 (arable areas) environmental pressures were selected as "priority areas". So these are the areas in Europe with the worst environmental problems. **Thus, EURAF estimates that the priority target area for new and regenerated agroforestry by 2030 is 12.8 Mha**³. The same dataset, which excludes protected areas (Natura 2000, Ramsar) and areas with existing agroforestry, has been analysed to identify areas (pixels) with only ONE environmental pressure. This produced an area of 119,890 million ha (arable 95.89 Mha, permanent grassland 24.00 Mha). **Thus, EURAF estimates the possible target area for new and regenerated agroforestry by 2030 is 119.9 Mha.**
4. **Current authors** suggest that targets for agroforestry can also be set using detailed tree cover density maps. There are very extensive areas of farmland in Europe with extremely low tree cover. These are often associated with environmental deficits such as erosion, nutrient and nitrate leaching, drought, and low levels of landscape and functional biodiversity. As an input to the Forestry Strategy, EURAF has provided maps of target areas for potential new agroforestry planting using 100x100m raster information from the **Copernicus Tree Cover Density 2015** system⁴, the **Corine Land Cover 2018** database (to provide an "agricultural" overlay⁵), and **Natura 2000/ Ramsar** databases (to exclude protected areas) (Table 1). Also shown are the proportion which these areas represent of total agricultural area (Table 2) and the distribution of low-tree-cover on agricultural land across "greater" Europe (Figure 1). Unfortunately the data cannot be averaged to NUTS levels because EUROSTAT only makes this available at the coarser resolution of NUTS2.

Table 1. Area (km²) of agricultural land with 0%, <1%, <2%, <5%, <10% tree cover for the year 2015 (EEA-39).

Corine class	Tree cover	0%	<1%	<2%	<5%	<10%	Total area (km2)
211 Non-irrigated arable land		962,804	969,374	982,468	1,013,740	1,039,933	1,212,620

¹ **Environmental risks** were found present on about 40% of the European arable land, and thus SAF could contribute to soil protection on 4%, to mitigate nitrate leaching on 18% and to increase landscape diversity on 32% of European arable land.

² **Arable land** - including short-term grass leys - covers 61.2% of EU27 utilised agricultural area (161.787 Mha), permanent grass 30.1% (50.137 Mha), permanent crops 7.5% (12.120 Mha) and kitchen gardens (0.562 Mha) 0.35%.

³ **UK and Croatia** are excluded in these estimates. Judging from neighbouring countries, an additional Priority area of 0.1 Mha could be added for Croatia.

⁴ **Tree Cover Density** data is provided by CORINE in a range from 0-100% for the 2012 and 2015 reference years. The data is available as raster data in European projection (EPSG: 3035) with 20 and 100m resolution. For our assessment we used the data with 100m resolution as we were interested in large areas with little or no tree cover. For our assessment we first constructed a map showing tree cover density in "agricultural areas". We then examined different thresholds for "no or very low tree cover" (0%, <1%, <2%, < 5%, <10%).

⁵ **Corine land cover classes** were used. The minimum mapping unit is 25ha for aerial phenomena and 100 metres for linear phenomena. We extracted "agricultural areas" to include second level classes 2.1 arable land, 2.2 permanent crops, 2.3 pastures, and 2.4 heterogeneous agricultural areas. In addition, we examined tree cover density in some of the most common individual third-level land cover classes (classes 2.1.1 non-irrigated arable land, 2.1.2 permanently irrigated land, 2.1.3 rice fields, and 2.3.1 pastures) to identify areas with low tree cover and thus a high potential for increasing tree cover. Tree cover density on class 2.4.4 agroforestry areas was also examined as a comparison.

212 Permanently irrigated land	93,809	94,725	95,773	97,808	99,852	109,331
213 Rice fields	6,012	6,045	6,103	6,235	6,355	8,210
231 Pastures	248,130	250,396	257,926	276,927	296,912	428,720
244 Agroforestry	4,478	5,824	6,645	8,493	11,179	33,083
2 All agricultural areas	1,686,407	1,709,746	1,749,513	1,843,090	1,945,852	2,445,287

We suggest that 1.69 million km² of European agricultural land⁶ has 0% tree cover (Table 1, Figure 1). An area of 1.71 million km² of agricultural land has less than 1% tree cover. An area of 1.9 million km² has less than 10% tree cover.

Table 2. Percentage agricultural land with 0%, <1%, <2%, <5%, <10% and >10% tree cover for 2015 (EEA-39).

Tree cover Corine class	0%	<1%	<2%	<5%	<10%	>10%
211 Non-irrigated arable land	84.5	85.0	86.2	88.9	91.7	9.3
212 Permanently irrigated land	88.6	89.4	90.4	92.4	94.3	5.7
213 Rice fields	89.6	90.1	91.0	93.0	94.8	5.2
231 Pastures	65.5	66.1	68.1	73.1	78.4	22.6
244 Agroforestry	13.5	17.6	20.1	25.6	33.8	66.2
2 All agricultural areas	68.8	69.8	71.4	75.2	79.4	20.6

Only 20% of the European agricultural area has more than 10% tree cover. 84.5% of non-irrigated arable land (Class 2.2.1) has zero tree cover, only 9.3% of this land has more than 10% tree cover. Table 2 shows that other arable classes have similar low levels of tree cover. Table 2 also shows that 34% of agroforestry land, as identified in the CORINE database, has tree crown densities below 10%. This identifies a need for the regeneration and management of traditional agroforestry systems, in addition to the planting of new areas.

For AF tree-planting densities, there is a need to plant 3-4 times more trees than the final stocking rate, since there is always a need to thin damaged trees or trees of poor quality during the life of the plantation. We estimate that a planting density of around 200 trees/ha is needed in silvoarable systems and 400 trees/ha in silvopastoral systems.

Table 3 shows our recommendation that **3.13 billion trees should be planted in areas of high environmental stress in Europe - a figure close to the total number of “extra trees” recommended in the Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020).**

Table 3. Calculated “Priority” and “Possible” areas for agroforestry to be planted or regenerated before 2030. Using the methodology of Kay et al., 2019. Planting densities assume a selective thinning rate of 3-4:1 to reach final stocking. The areas exclude the UK and Croatia. An additional 100.000 trees could be assumed for Croatia in the ‘Priority’ Scenario.

Scenario	Agroforestry System	Calculated Area (ha)	Planting Density/ha	Total trees (billion)
Priority Areas (4-5 environmental threats)	Silvoarable	9,959,142	200	1.99
	Silvopastoral	2,844,592	400	1.14
	Total			3.13
Possible Areas (1 environmental threat)	Silvoarable	95,890,000	200	19.18
	Silvopastoral	24,000,000	400	9.60
	Total			28.78

⁶ EEA-39 - Including EFTA members and EU Candidate States (inc. Turkey). This map will be replaced with EU-27

Figure 1. Priority planting areas, where tree cover density (% tree cover) on agricultural land is particularly low.
Source: Copernicus tree cover density 2015.

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